

The charter is the foundational document that describes the rationale, goals, plan of work, resources needed, terms and conditions, and outcomes of a Center for Digital Humanities at Princeton (hereafter CDH) project. Charters are written by core members of a project team in a series of planning meetings taking place over the course of a month. The planning process is intensive, collaborative and requires substantial input from everyone on a team. Charters serve as formalized agreements among all team members on such crucial questions as scope, technical design, infrastructural needs, and success criteria.

A draft of each project charter is peer-reviewed by all CDH staff, and optionally by additional partners or stakeholders, at a “design review” before the start of project work. It is circulated at least one week before the review takes place in an open comment period. Questions and concerns from this period may be raised at the design review. Project teams have two weeks after the design review to address any issues raised and make any requested changes. Project work only begins (and funds are released) once the charter has been finalized and signed by the Project Director (PI) and the CDH Faculty Director. Charters are amended as necessary throughout the project lifecycle to document major changes and note when “Built by CDH” Software Warranty and “Built by CDH” Long Term Service Agreement take effect, and serve as part of the CDH project archive.

CDH charters and their planning documents exist in several forms as we have refined them over the years and tailored them to the several types of projects we have supported. For more about CDH project management, including the charter process, visit: <https://cdh.princeton.edu/research/project-management/>

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Derrida's Margins: Annotations from the Personal Library of Jacques Derrida

Phase One: Of Grammatology

1. Project Description & Objectives

This project aims to create a website and online research tool for annotations from the Library of Jacques Derrida, housed at Princeton University Library. This phase focuses on annotations related to Derrida's landmark 1967 work *De la grammatologie* (Of Grammatology, hereafter *OG*). We begin by identifying all quotations and references in *OG*; we then locate these references in Derrida's copies of the works, transcribing all marginal annotations and other markings, and limiting ourselves to the parts of those works that are explicitly referenced. Digital images and transcriptions of these annotated pages will form the basis of the website, allowing users to go "behind the scenes" of Derrida's reading practices. This corpus will also serve as a pilot data set for future work, allowing us to establish protocols, workflow, and a relational database model.

2. Statement of Significance and Innovation

Jacques Derrida is one of the major figures of twentieth-century thought, and his library--which bears the traces of decades of close reading--represents a major intellectual archive. It was in *OG* that Derrida first articulated a new style of critical reading, which would become the foundation of the philosophy of "deconstruction." Our online research tool will enable scholars to study the development of this philosophy in an unprecedented way by providing comprehensive digital access to the material annotations, marginalia, bookmarks, and other notes from Derrida's library that correspond to each quotation and citation in *OG*.

3. Audience

Given that Derrida's work is widely read in the United States, France, and around the world by scholars from numerous disciplines in the humanities and social sciences, we anticipate that the audience for this project will be broad and international. The more targeted audience would be specialists of Derrida and deconstruction, as well as researchers in philosophy, literary studies, and intellectual history.

4) Project team:

PI: Katie Chenoweth

Project Manager: Alex Raiffe

Technical Leads: Jean Bauer and Rebecca Koeser

CDH Point Person: Jean Bauer and Rebecca Koeser

Web Designer: Xinyi Li

Annotation Projects Coordinator: Rebecca Munson

Student Team: Chloé Vettier, Chad Cordova, Jin Chow

Advisors: Eduardo Cadava, Avital Ronell (NYU)

5) Scope (of work/activities, of material/content)

Pages from all books quoted or cited in *Of Grammatology* found in Derrida's library at Princeton.

All of Derrida's own annotations (marginal notes, in-text markings) on the page are displayed, whether related to quoted/cited text or not. Pending clarification about copyright, for in-text markings, words in source text will be either be 1) blurred out; 2) displayed as images only, or 3) displayed as image and machine readable text.

Source text: Source text can range from a single word, to a block quote, to a whole page. Pending clarification about copyright, source text will either be fully displayed, or blurred out, except for sections quoted or cited directly in *Of Grammatology*.

Annotations will be transcribed, translated (when applicable), and tagged by type.

Work/activities: Establishing corpus for project; gaining familiarity with intellectual content; digitizing corpus; transcribing and tagging annotations; translating verbal annotations; designing and producing website; producing transcriber's manual for future transcribers.

Out of scope:

Content: volumes from the JD library not related to *OG*

Work/activities: Potentially providing translations of the text being referenced by the annotations? Also, interpretation might be out of the scope of this project, as we want to leave the interpretation of the significance of some of the annotations open-ended.

6) Main outcomes/deliverables with completion dates

- Bibliography of *De la grammatologie*, made available as public Zotero library (end of Summer 2016)
- Digitization of all relevant pages from the Derrida library (end of Summer 2016)
- Customized grayed-out images, if necessary (this will happen over the course of Fall 2016 as the work of transcribing takes place)
- Annotations transcribed, translated, and tagged (end of Spring 2017)
- Relational database (this will be progressively established over the course of the next academic year as work progresses on transcription)
- Website (end of Spring 2017)
- Transcriber's manual (end of Spring 2017)
- A scholarly conference (Spring 2017)

7) Success criteria

Our project will be a success if:

- a/ we have been able to digitize and tag the annotations from the works we have chosen as a pilot;
- b/ the website is operational and open to its target audience;
- c/ we have produced a Transcriber's Manual that will be of use to the next phase of digitization;
- d/ we have produced something that is theoretically interesting to scholars of Derrida and can be used as the basis for a scholarly conference and/or publication that will contribute to the study of deconstruction and/or Derrida.

8) Resource needs

- Project manager time
- Graduate research assistance
- Undergraduate research assistance
- Jean time
- Annotation project coordinator time
- Digitization (PUL)
- Designer for website
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9) Risks

The major risk for this project is the question of French copyright restrictions.

Due to the fact that the majority of books owned by Jacques Derrida are copyrighted works whose copyright is still in force, there is a question regarding the legality of posting digital images of sections of those books on our website. Despite the fact that the copies of these works in JD's library have been annotated by the philosopher's hand, the works themselves are the intellectual property of their respective publishing houses in France.

Pending clarification by the Office of the University Counsel regarding the amount of risk we are at liberty to take in this respect, we will make a decision as to the amount of text from those works that it is acceptable for us to display on our public website.

10) Interdependencies

RBSC/PUL

11) Project change process

Project changes will happen in coordination and discussion with our point persons from CDH and requests for change to the charter will be initiated by the PI, the PM, and the members of the team after collective discussion.

Once the project is in the implementation stage, any significant changes (such as scope, timeline, work plan, budget, etc.) must be discussed and approved by the PI and the CDH Associate Director. These changes will be recorded and appended to the project Charter.

12) Rights and permissions

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International](#), pending conversation with PU General Counsel re: copyright

13) Data security considerations

Nothing particular unless necessitated by copyright / access issues

14) Data management plan

Images will be held by the Princeton University Library
MySQL datadump available on CDH GitHub repository
Web framework code on GitHub

15) Post-grant plans for project

This project is intended as the first phase in a long-term project. We may apply for a Phase II grant for CDH; this decision will be made by December 2016. Going forward, we intend to apply for various grants, both internal (Magic) and external (NEH, Mellon), in order to extend the model developed around Of Grammatology to other works by Derrida.

Part II. Work Plan.

I. Research and locate relevant content; digitize corpus (July-August 2016)

- 1) Create public Zotero library of citations and quotations
 - a) Establish Zotero workflow & tagging conventions - June 20 (Jean, Katie, student researchers)
 - b) Populate Zotero library - 50 hours total; July, August (Jin, Chloe)
 - c) Check-in meeting with group - week of July 18th (Jean, student researchers)
- 2) Identify annotated pages based on citations - July, August (Jin, Chloe)
- 3) Establish list of books to be imaged - by end of August (Alex, Jin, Chloe, PUL)
- 4) Digital imaging - completed by end of September (PUL)

II. Design and population of database (Fall 2016)

- 1) Day-long seminar on intellectual content of work - 1-day meeting in September (PI, student researchers)
- 2) Database design & implementation
 - a) Database & workflow design - September, October, bi-weekly project team meetings (Jean, Lead Developer, student researchers)
 - b) Database implementation (November) - Lead Developer
- 3) Populating the database: transcription, translation and tagging - October-May (student researchers)

III. Application for funding for next phase (Dec/January/February)

CDH, Magic or external grant

IV. Completing database; Website development; Conference (Spring 2017)

- 1) Populating the database: transcription, translation and tagging - continues through May (student researchers)
- 2) Web framework development (Lead Developer, UX Designer) February-May
- 3) Conference (PI, student researchers)

V. Project wrap-up (Summer 2017)

- 1) Finalizing Transcriber's Manual (PI, student researchers) Complete by end of June
- 2) Write and submit Summary of Accomplishments to CDH (PI, PM) Complete by end of June

Part III Budget

[Budget available upon request.]

Part IV. Design Plan

The technical design has 4 main components

1. Zotero, the open source bibliographic management system, will be used for initial data capture to create a bibliography for Of Grammatology. Research assistants will use a custom set of tags to indicate whether a particular volume is in Derrida's personal library (as purchased by Princeton University), as well as presence or absence of annotation, and, type of annotation, whether annotations in the book correspond to citations in Of Grammatology. Once all this information has been recorded in Zotero, it will be exported for use in the standalone web framework.
2. A relational database (MySQL) custom built to model Derrida's annotation practices as they relate to books cited in his scholarship. Core modules include: Derrida's annotation system (types of marks on pages, transcriptions and translations of verbal annotations or underlined anchor text) and citations within Of Grammatology. The system will be designed to handle additional works by Derrida as the project moves forward. Though written in SQL, the database will be designed to be exposed as Linked Open Data (RDF and/or JSON-LD).
3. The Princeton University Library image store and IIIF compliant image server for archival quality photographs of annotated pages. If copyright constraints prohibit us from showing the full page, the project will create customize greyed out images that allow users to see the presence and density of annotation on a page.
4. A web framework (probably Django or Ruby on Rails) to pull the relational database and images together into a single open access web platform for search, browse, and display purposes. The images will be displayed using a IIIF compliant viewer (most likely the

Universal Viewer). The site (including search) will be fully bilingual, French and English. The site will also have an API for serving Linked Open Data (RDF and/or JSON-LD).

The system will be built on the CDH development server in a controlled virtual environment (Vagrant or Docker). It is extremely likely that the Princeton University Library will want to host the completed site.

Data Release to include:

- Public Zotero Library featuring bibliography of Of Grammatology
 - Mysqldump of relational database with readme file describing original project
 - Documentation for working with the API
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Part V: Agreement

This document commits the PI and the CDH to the terms elaborated in the Charter, and reflects mutual agreement regarding the necessary deliverables, responsibilities, and timeline for project success.

Rights, Permissions, and Attribution

We intend Derrida's Margins: Annotations from the Personal Library of Jacques Derrida. Phase One: Of Grammatology to be an open-access project, published under the Creative Commons [Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/) license, pending conversation with PU General Counsel regarding copyright.

Web presence and project publicity

The PI will create a publicity page on the CDH website, keeping it up-to-date and accurate during the grant year. The project team will submit at least one blog posts per semester, to be published on the CDH website. The schedule for publishing blog posts is set by the CDH at the beginning of each semester.

Credit

All team members will be credited on the project's website and CDH publicity page. The project's website will include a sponsorship statement (indicating the CDH as well as any other supporting groups, departments, agencies) and will include a citation statement indicating how the project assets should be cited.

End-of-grant plan

The PI will submit the Summary of Accomplishments to the CDH Project Manager at the conclusion of the grant cycle.

Project PI(s)

CDH Associate Director

Date: